

WALTER JOHNSON

God's Knowledge in Our Frail Mind: The Thomistic Model of Theology

Essays in « ANGELICUM » LXXVI (1999), pp. 25-46

2
HOUR

PERIODICUM TRIMESTRE PONTIFICIAE STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITATIS A SANCTO THOMA AQUINATE IN URBE

LARGO ANGELICUM 1
00184 ROMA
1999

M
5091

God's Knowledge in Our Frail Mind: The Thomistic Model of Theology

SUMMARY

We speak of St. Thomas's account of the nature of theology as a 'science,' largely because of the influx of Aristotle's scientific writings in the 12th and 13th centuries, in particular the Posterior Analytics. This aspect of Thomas's teaching has been emphasized in the literature, largely because of the influence of Chenu's *La théologie comme science*. Yet considering theology to be a science is helpful only up to a point, for Thomas wishes to characterize sacred theology as somewhat like the very knowledge that God possesses of things, for which he employs the notion of wisdom, an intellectual virtue that surpasses what science, in the Aristotelian sense, is capable of.

« Lumen... fidei... est quasi quaedam sigillatio primae veritatis in mente » (*In Boetii de trinitate*, q. 3, a. 1, ad 4).

« Et sic [doctrina fidei] est perfectior: utpote Dei cognitioni similior, qui seipsum cognoscens alia intuetur » (*Summa contra gentiles*, lib. 2, cap. 4).

« ...ut sic sacra doctrina sit velut quaedam impressio divinae scientiae, quae est una et simplex omnium » (*Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 2, ad 2).

« ...per potentiam intellectivam homo participat cognitionem divinam per virtutem fidei » (*Summa theologiae*, I-II, q. 110, a. 4, in corp).

Because of the continuing influence of a theologian such as Avery Dulles, it has become customary in theology today to employ the notion of 'models' when speaking of theological items ranging from revelation to the Church, ⁽¹⁾ and Dulles's book, *The*

⁽¹⁾ See DULLES's books of the same name: *Models of Revelation*, (Garden

Craft of Theology: From Symbol to System, which he considered naming *Models of Theology*, continues this trend.⁽²⁾ Employing 'models', as Dulles notes, can be useful in initiating and sustaining dialogue among theologians from widely differing schools of thought, and these theologians would then have an idea as to the wider, theological framework of their interlocutors, thus yielding, one reckons, less confusion and greater understanding.

With this in mind, I would like in this article to present what I take to be St. Thomas Aquinas's 'model' of theology, a model which, I believe, could prove quite intriguing to readers of his works. Students of Thomas's thought know that his description of theology has been the cause of much discussion and indeed disagreement in the literature, so I shall start with a brief reconsideration of some of that literature as a kind of dialectical introduction to my broader thesis — what have others said? My thesis is that Thomas's model of theology is not, as it is traditional to assert, a 'science,' but is rather a 'wisdom,' a wisdom with a distinct character. More than that, I suggest that the model for this wisdom is none other than the divine knowledge itself. The model for Thomas's notion of theology is 'God's knowledge in our frail minds.'

A LOOK BACK AT THE LITERATURE

Since Thomas's fullest and final treatment of the nature of theology or 'sacred doctrine' (*sacra doctrina*) is found at the outset of his *Summa theologiae*, it was natural enough that the

City, N.Y.: Doubleday, 1983), *Models of the Church*, 2nd ed. (Garden City, N.Y.: Doubleday, 1987). Similarly one notes books like SALLIE MCFARGUE's *Models of God* (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1987), JOHN F. O'GRADY's *Models of Jesus* (Garden City, N.Y.: Doubleday, 1981), and RAYMOND F. COLLIN's *Models of Theological Reflection* (Lanham, Md.: University Press of America, 1984). For the sake of convenience, all works cited will appear at first in full form, and there after cited in abbreviated form. All translations from Latin are my own.

⁽²⁾ See AVERY DULLES, S.J., *The Craft of Theology: From Symbol to System*, (New York: Crossroad Publishing, Co., 1992), p. 41.

accounts of his teaching given by the commentary tradition be found in commentaries on the *Summa* as well.⁽³⁾ And so they were.⁽⁴⁾ Building upon these commentatorial accounts, M.-D. Chenu brought to bear his historical skills in his magisterial monograph, *La Théologie comme science au XIII^e siècle*, which enjoyed three separate printings,⁽⁵⁾ and to which all subsequent

⁽³⁾ The places in which Thomas discusses sacred doctrine or theology, and their dates (see J.-P. TORRELL, *St. Thomas Aquinas: The Person and His Work*, trans. R. Royal [Washington, DC: CUA Press, 1996], 330-59), are the following: *In I Sent.* (1252), prol., aa. 1-5; *Expositio in librum Boethii de trinitate* (1956), q. 2; *ibid.*, q. 5, a. 4; *Summa contra gentiles* (1260), lib. 1, cc. 1-9; *Summa theologiae* (1265) I, q. 1, aa. 1-10. A student report, or *reportatio*, of classroom lectures Thomas gave in Rome in 1265 survives in an Oxford manuscript, and is now dubbed 'the Roman commentary.' For an account of this *reportatio* or 'Roman commentary' on Book 1 of the *Sentences*, with a list of the texts found in it, see my « *Alia lectura fratris thome: A List of the New Texts of St Thomas Aquinas found in Lincoln College, Oxford, MS. Lat. 95,* » *Recherches de théologie ancienne et médiévale* 57 (1990): 34-61. A critical edition of these texts is underway by John F. Boyle, and Leonard E. Boyle. There are seven articles in the student report that concern theology, listed as articles 7-13 on pp. 43-44 of the article just cited.

⁽⁴⁾ The three Dominican Thomistic commentators usually consulted, and their commentaries, are: THOMAS DE VIO CAJETANUS, or CAJETAN (1469-1534), *Commentarium in primam partem Summae Theologiae Sancti Thomae Aquinatis*, in *Sancti Thomae Aquinatis Opera Omnia*, vol. 4, ed. Leonine (Rome: Propaganda Fide, 1888), pp. 6-26; DOMINGO BÁÑEZ (1528-1604), *Scholastica commentaria in primam partem Summae Theologiae S. Thomae Aquinatis*, ed. Luis Urbano (Madrid: Editorial F.E.D.A., 1934), pp. 7-99; and JOHN OF ST THOMAS (1589-1644), *Cursus theologicus*, vol. 1, ed. Solemnes (Paris: Desclée, 1931), pp. 143-219; 305-410. One could add to these JOHANNES CAPREOLUS's (1380-1444) *Defensiones theologiae Divi Thomae Aquinatis*, eds. C. Paban and T. Pègues (Tours: Alfred Cattier, 1900), pp. 1-61, although his commentary takes the form of a traditional *scriptum* on PETER LOMBARD's *Libri sententiarum* - it was written for Dominicans who were to be *Bachallares sententiarum*. According to tradition, CONRAD KÖLLIN (1476-1536) also had produced a commentary on the first part of the *Summa theologiae*, but it unfortunately has been lost. See the entry for Köllin in *Scriptores ordinis praedicatorum*, tomus 2, eds. J. Quéatif and J. Échard, (Paris: Ballard-Simart, 1721), fol. 100a-b. Köllin's commentary on the *Prima pars* would have been the only one not significantly influenced by Cajetan.

⁽⁵⁾ M.-D. CHENU, « *La Théologie comme science au xiii^e siècle* », *Archives d'Histoire Doctrinale et Littéraire du Moyen-âge* 2 (1927): 31-71;

scholarship on this issue has since in some way or another referred. ⁽⁶⁾

It was a principal goal of Chenu's to establish that Thomas was the first medieval theologian fully to apply the Aristotelian notion of science to sacred doctrine. Thomas's novelty in this respect led Chenu to the further, correct claim that theology in Thomas's mind is a subalternated science, which receives as true its principles from the higher science of God's knowledge, and which can then proceed to deduce new conclusions contained virtually in the premises, which are the articles of the faith.

La Théologie comme science au xiii^e siècle, 2nd ed. (Paris: J. Vrin, 1942). The third edition was published as well by J. Vrin in 1957.

⁽⁶⁾ See J.-FR. BONNEFOY, *La Nature de la théologie selon Saint Thomas d'Aquin*, (Paris: Vrin, 1939); G. VAN ACKEREN, *Sacra Doctrina: The Subject of the First Question of the Summa Theologica of St. Thomas Aquinas*, (Rome: Catholic Book Agency, 1952); J. A. WEISHEIPL, « The Meaning of *Sacra Doctrina* in *Summa theologiae* I, q. 1, » *The Thomist* 38 (1974): 49-80; T. C. O'BRIEN, « *Sacra Doctrina* revisited: The Context of Medieval Education, » *The Thomist* 41 (1977): 475-509; and from a Protestant perspective, PER ERIK PERSSON, *Sacra doctrina: Reason and Revelation in Aquinas*, trans. R. Mackenzie (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1970). For more recent works treating of Thomas's notion of theology, see: M. F. SPARROW, « Natural Knowledge of God and the Principles of 'Sacra Doctrina', » *Angelicum* 69 (1992): 471-491; JOHN JENKINS, CSC, *Knowledge and Faith in Thomas Aquinas* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997); GEOFFREY TURNER, « St Thomas Aquinas on the 'Scientific' Nature of Theology, » *New Blackfriars* 78 (1997): 464-476. I take the liberty of referring to my *The Sapiential Character of Sacra Doctrina in the Thought of St Thomas Aquinas: The Appropriation of Aristotle's Intellectual Virtue of Wisdom*, unpublished doctoral dissertation (Toronto: University of Toronto, 1990). For a shorter presentation see my « The Sapiential Character of the First Article of the *Summa theologiae*, » in *Philosophy and the God of Abraham: Essay in Memory of James A. Weisheipl, OP*, (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1991), pp. 85-98. Other comments can be found in my « Why Five Ways?, » in *Religion and the Virtue of Religion: Proceedings of the American Catholic Philosophical Association*, vol. 65 (Washington, DC: The American Catholic Philosophical Association, 1992), pp. 107-21. See also J.-P. TORRELL's marvelous general overview, « Le savoir théologique chez saint Thomas, » *Revue Thomiste* 96 (1996): 355-396, and « Le savoir théologique chez saint Thomas, » *Revue Thomiste* 96 (1996): 355-396, and « Le savoir théologique chez les premiers thomistes, » *ibid.*, 97 (1997): 9-30. Torrell also refers to others authors I consulted in preparation for this article.

Impressed by this new, scientific model of the theological enterprise, Chenu carefully drew out its implications⁽⁷⁾ and subsequent considerations of Thomas's account of sacred doctrine almost universally took his interpretation as good money.

Almost universally, as we will see. Chenu, as it happened, had been so taken with Thomas's appropriation of the scientific model, together with its demonstrative deductions, that when he encountered texts in the *Summa theologiae* that did not fit into his interpretation, he dismissed them as historically-required excursions on Thomas's part. So, when he dealt with article 1 of question 1 of the *Summa theologiae*, where Thomas is providing the rationale for the existence of theology or sacred doctrine, and, similarly, when he dealt with articles 9 and 10 of the same question, where Thomas discusses the nature and role of sacred scripture, Chenu thought that this amounted to a breakdown in the flow of the text, a *rupture du contexte*. If Thomas had been true to his understanding of sacred doctrine as an Aristotelian science, he wouldn't have written those articles. Why? Because those articles concern the establishment of theological principles, something which a 'science' does not do, least of all a subalternated science, which receives its principles from a higher science, where the principles are established through self-evidence or demonstration, and explained.⁽⁸⁾ These conclusions of the superior science, however, are received as principles or starting-points by the lower, subalternated science, and are merely accepted as true by that subalternated science. What Thomas was doing, Chenu thought, was allowing the subalternated science of theology to usurp the tasks of the superior, subalternating science of God's knowledge from which it draws its principles.

⁽⁷⁾ See CHENU, « *La Théologie comme science*, » 1st ed., p. 33: « l'Écriture, l'article de foi est non plus la matière même, le sujet de l'exposé et de la recherche, comme dans la sacra doctrina du xii^e siècle, mais le principe, préalablement connu... partir duquel on travaille, et travaille selon toutes les exigences et les lois de la démonstration aristotélicienne. Tel est le sens profond de la première question de la *Somme* ».

⁽⁸⁾ For more on subalternation, see TORRELL, « *Le savoir théologique*, » pp. 385-388, and LEO ELDERS, « *Saint Thomas et la méthode scholastique*, » *Doctor Communis* 49 (1996): 191-218, at 213-218.

And to do this is to fracture the notion of science operative in question 1. This disorder called for an explanation, because Thomas seemed not to be faithful to the internal logic of his new model for theology, so Chenu explained these 'unscientific' moments by saying that Thomas was adhering to the practice of his time, according to which the theologian always discusses scripture and its senses. In time, if Thomas's model carried the day, there would be no need for such explicatory articles. (9)

This was, in a way, a startling claim, at least because it would seem to require that Thomas forget, but a few pages into the *Summa theologiae*, one of the very reasons he wrote the work. Thomas undertook the writing of the *Summa* largely because he disliked the disorder of other such summaries of Christian teaching. (10) His goal was to produce a work that

(9) *Ibid.*, pp. 68-69: « De cette ambiguïté [i.e., the awkwardness of article 1], bien inoffensive désormais, et de cette conception périmée de la doctrine sacrée, un second cas est plus notable: c'est le fait même de la présence, dans une question traitant de la nature de la "science" théologique, de deux longs articles sur le genre littéraire de l'Écriture (*Utrum sacra scriptura debeat uti metaphoris*, a. 9) et sur ses règles d'interprétation (*Utrum sacra scriptura sub una littera habeat plures sensus*, a. 10). Il est clair que c'est la matière se rapportant à l'établissement même de donné révélé et des articles de foi, principes de la science théologique; c'est donc matière préalable à la "science" dont on veut ici définir la méthode, et non établir le donné. Aussi, après les articles 2 et 8 surtout, le lecteur moderne sent-il vivement la rupture du contexte, en abordant l'article 9 sur la convenance du style métaphorique de la Bible. Là encore, l'explication nous paraît facile: puisqu'il était reçu, à l'entrée de la doctrine sacrée, de traiter des sens de l'Écriture, saint Thomas se conforme à l'usage, que pourtant, bientôt, la logique interne de sa théorie éliminera. On observa d'ailleurs que déjà cet exposé d'herméneutique sacrée n'est plus, comme dans le *Commentaire des Sentences* (q. 1, a. 5), bloqué en un seul article avec l'exposé de la méthode théologique. Le temps fera le reste. »

(10) See *Summa theologiae*, I, prol. in *Sancti Thomae de Aquinas Summa Theologiae*, ed. Ottawa: Medieval Institute, 1953), vol. 1, p. 1: « Consideravimus namque huius doctrinae novitios in his quae a diversis conscripta sunt plurimum impediri; partim quidem propter multiplicationem inutilium quaestionum, articulorum et argumentorum; partim etiam quia ea quae sunt necessaria talibus ad sciendum non traduntur ordinem disciplinae, sed secundum quod requirebat librorum expositio, vel secundum se praebebat occasio disputandi; partim quidem quia eorundum

would, for once, be free from pedagogical disarray, a charge against him that lies implicit in Chenu's assertion of a breakdown in question 1.

More than being a procedural complaint, Chenu's claim also gives rise to the disturbing contention that considerations of sacred scripture (aa. 9-10), as well as meditation upon the rationale for certain basic Christian teachings (a. 1), do not belong in theology as Thomas understood it. Yet scripture was the book used for theological teaching in the middle ages, (11) and Thomas's numerous scriptural commentaries are the literary remnants of his professional theological teaching. (12) This upshot of Chenu's understanding, grounded though it was in the impressive spadework of the medievalist, should have been, I believe, more unsettling to the scholarly community than it was.

frequens repetitio et fastidium et confusionem generabat in animis auditorum. Haec igitur et alia huiusmodi evitare studentes, tantabimus, cum confidentia divini auxilii, ea quae ad sacram doctrinam pertinent breviter ac dilucide prosequi, secundum quod materia patietur.» For more on the context surrounding the writing of the *Summa theologiae*, see L. E. BOYLE, *The Setting of the Summa theologiae of St Thomas*, (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1982).

(11) See HENRI DENIFLE, « Quel livre servait de base à l'enseignement des Maîtres en Théologie dans l'Université de Paris, » *Revue Thomiste* 2 (1894): 129-161.

(12) See JAMES A. WEISHEIPL, *Friar Thomas d'Aquino: His Life, Thought, and Work*, 2nd ed. with corrigenda and addenda (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press), pp. 110-111. It was Alexander of Hales who first introduced the non-scriptural *Sentences* as a teaching textbook in theology, for which he was roundly condemned by Roger Bacon (see the fourth of Bacon's seven 'sins' in the study of theology in his *Opus minus* [*Fr. Rogeri Bacon: Opera Quaedam Hactenus Inedita*, ed. J. S. Brewer (London: Longman, 1859), vol. 1, p. 328]) - but then, who wasn't roundly condemned by Roger Bacon?

As an aside one might also note that Thomas regularly uses the terms *sacra doctrina* and *sacra scriptura* interchangeably. See the following texts: *In I Sent.*, prol., q. 3, a. 2, arg. 1 and *sed contra*; *In Boethii de trinitate*, q. 2, a. 3, *in corp.*, ad 5 and ad 8; *ibid.*, q. 5, a. 4, *in corp.*, and ad 3; *Summa theologiae* I, q. 1, a. 2, arg. 2, and ad 2; a. 4, arg. 2; *ibid.*, I, q. 1, a. 7, arg. 2 and ad 2; I, q. 1, a. 9, ad 1. Though such verbal usage was common in his day, it nonetheless indicates the mutual intimacy, if not identity, of theology and the tasks of studying scripture - and on this Chenu was surely right regarding the medieval tradition of the teaching of theology as largely an exercise in scriptural exegesis.

Yet, there were a few dissenting voices, I believe the first of which was that of the Spanish Dominican, Santiago Ramírez. ⁽¹³⁾ Others followed, such as those of Francisco Muñiz, William Wallace, Kieran Conley, and James Weisheipl, all taking their lead from Ramírez's comments. ⁽¹⁴⁾ The substance of Ramírez's demur was that Chenu, while correct in claiming that theology was a science for Thomas, had incorrectly confined theology to that classification, whereas Thomas in question 1, article 6, is clear in asserting that theology is a wisdom in *addition* to its being a science. And because theology is a wisdom, and not just a science, it has tasks that exceed those performed by a science, since, as wisdom, it must explain and defend the principles from which it, after the fashion of a science, deduces new conclusions. Far from being historically-necessitated intrusions into the presentation of sacred doctrine in question 1, the articles under discussion are in fact required by the internal logic of Thomas's notion of theology. A true 'breakdown' in question 1 could only have been noticed if those articles had been absent. ⁽¹⁵⁾

⁽¹³⁾ J. M. RAMÍREZ, *De hominis beatitudine*, vol. 1, in *Jacobus M. Ramírez, O.P.: Opera Omnia*, ed. Victorino Radríguez, vol. 3, tomos 1 (Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, 1972), p. 7, note 1.

⁽¹⁴⁾ See FRANCISCO MUÑIZ, «De diversis muneribus S. Theologiae secundum doctrinam D. Thomae,» *Angelicum* 24 (1947): 93-123, translated by J. P. Reid as *The Work of Theology* (Washington: The Thomist Press, 1953); WILLIAM A. WALLACE, *The Role of Demonstration in Moral Theology: A Study of Methodology in St. Thomas Aquinas*, (Washington, D.C.: The Thomist Press, 1962), pp. 57-70; KIERAN CONLEY, *A Theology of Wisdom: A Study in St. Thomas* (Dubuque: The Priory Press, 1963); J. A. WEISHEIPL, «The Meaning of *Sacra Doctrina*.»

⁽¹⁵⁾ See RAMÍREZ, *De hominis beatitudine*, vol. 1, p. 7, n. 1, where, after citing CHENU's «La Théologie,» he remarks: «Simul tamen, et plus quam scientia presse sumpta, Sacra theologia est vera sapientia, inmo est 'maxima sapientia inter omnes sapientias humanas, non quidem in aliquo genere tantum, sed simpliciter' (I, q. 1, a. 6). Quapropter, non abusive, sed ex proprio munere ei convenit, non solum conclusiones deducere ex principiis per demonstrationem, sed etiam critiche exponere seu explicare propria principia eaque ab impugnatoribus et corruptoribus defendere. Hoc enim addit sapientia supra meram scientiam (I-II, q. 57, a. 1; q. 66, a. 5; I, q. 1, a. 6, and a. 8). Quod si ita est, articuli 9-10, et similiter articulus 1, non sunt 'ruptura contextus' (Chenu, p. 69); quin potius eos eliminare esset magnam rupturam textus et contextus perficere, quia postulantur neces-

Ramírez's critique of Chenu is solid, I believe, and it helps to pave the way for a fuller understanding of the meditative dynamism of Thomas's notion of theology, a dynamism, I would add, that is not at all refractory to the Aristotelian models that serve as its base. ⁽¹⁶⁾

THEOLOGY AS THOMAS UNDERSTOOD IT

The general 'movement' of question 1 of the *Summa theologiae* amounts to, I would suggest, an application on Thomas's part of the Aristotelian scientific method that the philosopher sketches in his *Posterior Analytics*. In the method, one first begins to see whether there actually exists the reality under discussion, this being the scientific question 'does it exist?' (*an sit?*). Once it has been established that there is such a thing, one initiates an investigation into the nature of the thing, asking questions 'how is it?' or 'in what way is it?' (*quomodo sit?*), until one has a grasp of the nature or 'whatness' of the particular thing, its 'what is it?' (*quid sit?*). This knowledge of the nature of the thing under consideration leads to questions regarding its features or characteristics, which can be ascertained because of the knowledge, now possessed, of the nature of the thing (*propter quid sit*). ⁽¹⁷⁾ According to this approach, Thomas in

sario ex ipsa 'logica interna' theoriae de sapientia maxime et simpliciter dicta.»

⁽¹⁶⁾ In fairness to Father Chenu I should point out that he did not persist in holding the «rupture du contexte,» for in both the second and third editions of *La théologie* one does not find the assertion — though Chenu does not draw attention to the omissions in the later editions, and perforce does not draw attention to why, precisely, he had changed his mind. See *La théologie*, 3rd ed., p. 79, which covers the material originally published in the 1927 edition at pp. 68-69. And in fact chapter 6 of the 3rd edition is entitled «science et sagesse,» though it does not cover the material in the way I shall cover it below.

⁽¹⁷⁾ See Aristotle's presentation of the four scientific questions, in his *Posterior Analytics*, bk. 2, cap. 1. Thomas's commentary on the four questions is to be found in his *Expositio libri posteriorum*, I, 2, cap. 1, ad 89b23-90a23, in *Sancti Thomae de Aquino Opera Omnia*, vol. 1/2, 2nd ed.,

article 1 provides an explanation as to why sacred doctrine should exist at all, given that other disciplines would seem to provide a consideration of God, or given that the difficulty of studying the divine seems to militate against the possibility of true knowledge in divine matters. Once he has given a rationale for the existence of sacred doctrine, in articles 2-7 he seeks the essential nature of sacred doctrine in a 'hunt for the definition' (*venatio definitionis*), a definition that Thomas uses in articles 8-10 in explaining the characteristics of sacred doctrine, its 'manner' or 'mode' (*modus*).⁽¹⁸⁾

It is in article 2 that Thomas asks the question whether sacred doctrine is a science, and it is here that difficulties can arise. The context of this article, following article 1 as it does, is such that Thomas is just beginning his search for the complete definition of sacred doctrine. It would be quite unusual if Thomas were immediately to provide his reader with a most detailed account of the classification into which theology could be put. Rather, since article 1 has scrupulously used the term 'teaching' in its deliberations — 'whether it is necessary that there be, beyond the philosophical disciplines, another teaching?' — Thomas in article 2 is concerned to place sacred teaching in a broad classification that will succeed in distinguishing it from other 'teachings' and yet allow for its further specification in subsequent articles. The notion of 'science' accomplished this, since it explains that sacred doctrine proceeds from certain knowledge, namely that of God and of the Blessed, though we who possess it in this life attain to the knowledge of God only through faith, not direct vision.⁽¹⁹⁾ And it is because of this requirement

ed. Leonine (Romae: Ad Sanctae Sabinae, 1989), pp. 174-177. See also *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 2, a. 2, sed contra; q. 3, prolog.

⁽¹⁸⁾ Parenthetically, I would have liked to see John Jenkins, in the fine book referred to above, note 6, to have emphasized Thomas's structure in question 1 more than he did (pp. 85-90), for doing so would have resulted, I believe, in a fuller, more meditative account of how theology functions for Thomas.

⁽¹⁹⁾ See *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 2, in corp. It is important to note that no form of the word 'concludere' appears in this article, although Chenu's approach would have to call for its presence. It was Cajetan,

of 'certain knowledge' that Thomas uses the notion of 'subalternation' to explain how it is that the teaching of sacred doctrine can proceed from truths that are not directly (*per se*) known, although that usually obtains in other sciences; the truths employed in sacred doctrine are directly known to God and to the Blessed, and are received by us in this life, believing the God who reveals them to us. In this way theology is somewhat like say, optics, which receives truths from the science of geometry and applies them to, in the case of optics, visible lines.⁽²⁰⁾

The most important contribution of article 2, it seems to me, is that it seeks to establish that sacred doctrine is a discipline that can possess cognitional certitude despite the fact that its principles are not immediately evident. As Thomas notes in his commentary on Lombard's *Sentences*: «...not every cognition, but only a certain one, is called 'science'.»⁽²¹⁾ And this is why

I suspect, who first began to take this article as the more refined classification of theology, and who, I think, put the cart before the horse in so doing. See his commentary on this article, in *Commentarium in primam partem summae theologiae*, q. 1, a. 2, no. 1, p. 9, in the edition cited above, page 17, note 4: «...scientia enim hic proprie, ut est intellectualis virtus et habitus conclusionum per demonstrationem; ...sacra doctrina hic sumitur pro doctrina revelata ut est conclusionum.»

⁽²⁰⁾ Thomas's use of the model of the 'subalternation' of sacred theology would constitute the one instance where a subalternation by reason of the principles of knowledge (*ratione principiorum*) is not the result of a prior subalternation by reason of subject matter (*ratione subiecti*), as happens in mixed sciences, like optics and mathematical physics. See *Summa theologiae* I, q. 1, a. 2; II-II, q. 1, a. 6; *De veritate*, q. 14, a. 9; *In Boethii de trinitate*, q. 2, a. 2, ad 5 and ad 7; and especially *In I sent.*, prolog., a. 3, qua. 2, in corp.

⁽²¹⁾ *In I sent.*, prolog., a. 3, qua. 2, in corp., in *S. Thomae Aquinatis Scriptum super libros sententiarum*, ed. Mandonnet (Paris: Lethielleux, 1929), vol. 1, p. 13: «...non quaelibet cognitio, sed certitudinalis tantum dicitur scientia.» While it might be perhaps inappropriate to cite an earlier text to explain a later one — Thomas's *Scriptum on the Sentences* dates from 1252, while the *Prima pars* of the *Summa theologiae* dates from 1265-1266 — this text, though found in the Parisian commentary on the *Sentences*, is a later, authentic insertion from Thomas himself, which may actually post-date the treatment of theology found in the *Prima pars* of the *Summa theologiae*. See E. BOOTH, «The Three Pecia Systems of St. Thomas Aquina's Commentary *In I Sententiarum*», in *La production du livre universitaire au moyen âge: Exempla et pecia*, (Paris: Éditions du

the first objected difficulty at the outset of the article complains that the principles of sacred doctrine are not immediately evident to all, and in fact would be disputed by those who do not accept the articles of faith that serve as the starting-points for theology. If Thomas were unable to establish that theology is a discipline possessed of certitude, albeit a derived certitude, then any hope of assessing truth or falsity in claims regarding the Faith would be non-existent. His ability to explain that the principles of sacred doctrine *are* immediately evident to those from whom we receive them, lets him proceed to establish the domain of this study, and its method, and what the possibilities are for the generation of further, certain knowledge.⁽²²⁾

Thomas sets tasks for himself in articles 3 through 7, which gradually refine the notion of sacred doctrine. Article 3 addresses the question of how sacred doctrine can be a united knowledge, covering a single domain, given the multiplicity of formally diverse items it concerns itself with: God, creatures, human actions, angels, on and on. In reply Thomas emphasizes theology's single 'point of view,' namely that all the things it considers because of their being divinely revealed (*divinitus revelata*), and are hence unified in that respect. Sacred theology is both a practical and a speculative science (article 4), but it is speculative by priority because of its ultimate end, the perfect knowledge of God to be had in heaven. Its dignity surpasses that of the other sciences (article 5), both because it concerns itself with higher things, and because the source of its certitude, God's knowledge, is higher than the natural reason that serves as the basis for the certitude of the other disciplines.

If it is true to say that the purpose of article 2 was to place sacred doctrine in a broad classification — what the scholastic tradition would call its 'remote genus' — then it would be also be true to say that the purpose of article 6 is to explain the most

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, 1988), pp. 225-252. Thomas continues to employ this nuanced understanding of 'science.' See *In I Post. Anal.*, lect. 7, ad 72b18, p. 31.

⁽²²⁾ See *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 2, ad 1.

narrow classification, or 'proximate genus,' for sacred doctrine. Is sacred doctrine a wisdom? Thomas says 'yes.'⁽²³⁾ But the wisdom of sacred doctrine is, in fact, a higher wisdom than any human wisdom, for the 'height' of a human wisdom is assessed according to the 'height' of the causes it considers, and in virtue of which causes it makes its various judgments. Now the 'height' of the cause sacred doctrine considers is as high as could be, for it is the highest cause of the whole universe, none other than God himself. And even in its consideration of God sacred doctrine surpasses the human wisdom of metaphysics, which also considers God, for the principles sacred doctrine uses in its undertaking come directly from God, while those of metaphysics come from natural knowledge obtained from examination of the created order. And thus the hallmarks of wisdom as Thomas understood it, ordering and judgment, in sacred doctrine proceed from the very highest point of departure, that of God: « sacred doctrine concerns itself with God... also with respect to what is known to him alone about himself, and communicated to others through revelation. »⁽²⁴⁾

In the next section I shall explain the features, the functions, of the theologian as 'the wise person' in greater detail. But for now suffice it to say that Thomas's modeling theology as a wisdom, coupled with the sheer height of the theologian's point of view — namely, its specific difference's being that it is about God (article 7) and directly from God — already means that the tasks of theology in Thomas's mind far exceed the mere deduction of new truths implicitly contained in the articles of faith that serve as the principles for theological science — this being the kind of characterization that would ensue from a slavish adherence to Chenu's claims in the first edition of « La

⁽²³⁾ This is, in actuality, Thomas's constant teaching from the outset of his writing career. See *In I Sent.*, prol., a. 3, qua. 1, in corp.: « Et, cum habitus speculativi sint tres, secundum Philosophum, VI *Ethicorum*, dicimus quod est sapientia, eo quod altissimas causas considerat et est sicut caput et principalis et ordinatrix omnium scientiarum... » See also *In Boethii de trin.*, q. 2, a. 2, ad 1.

⁽²⁴⁾ *Summa theologiae*, I, 1, q. a. 6, in corp.

théologie.»⁽²⁵⁾ Thomas's subsequent discussion of the 'argumentative' character of theology, in article 8, does note that sacred doctrine argues to 'other things that are handed on' in the faith.⁽²⁶⁾ But his likening theology to the human wisdom of metaphysics in the body of the article should encourage his reader to think of these 'other things' as including *more* than new truths or dogma, previously unknown. It can well include a delineation of the connections *among* the various revealed truths of faith, or a presentation of the notions requisite for an understanding of truths of faith. Thomas's immediate consideration, in articles 9 and 10, of the nature of the resources of sacred doctrine, sacred scripture, which he considers the proper authority of sacred doctrine,⁽²⁷⁾ is an outgrowth, I shall later point out, of this understanding of theology.

THE TASKS OF THE THEOLOGIAN AS 'WISE'

Thomas's teaching on the nature of 'wisdom' is to be found in no single place in his writings, and must, if it is to be known and employed at all, be gleaned from various passages throughout the Thomistic literary corpus.⁽²⁸⁾ The result of such a gleaning leads to the following three tasks specific to wisdom: 1) the contemplation of the absolutely highest cause, God; 2) an account and ordering of the first principles of the discipline; 3) a

⁽²⁵⁾ Again, I note that Chenu did change his mind on this topic (see above, p. 22, note 16), and that I use the history of his editions of «La théologie» as *topos* for my consideration of Thomas's teaching.

⁽²⁶⁾ *Ibid.*, a. 8, ad 2.

⁽²⁷⁾ See *ibid.*: «Auctoritatibus autem canonicae Scripturae utitur [sacra doctrina] proprie, ex necessitate argumentando...»

⁽²⁸⁾ For more synthetic accounts of Thomas's teaching on the nature of wisdom, see my *The Sapiential Character of Sacra Doctrina*, pp. 70-106; CONLEY, *A Theology of Wisdom*, pp. 29-58; MUÑIZ, *De diversis muneribus S. Theologiae*, passim; and especially SANTIAGO RAMÍREZ's *De ipsa philosophia in univsum*, 2.2., in *Jacobus M. Ramírez, O.P.: Opera Omnia*, ed. Victorino Rodríguez, vol. 1, tomos 1 (Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, 1970), pp. 333-373.

defense of those principles when attacked. Thomas makes clear that wisdom has the function of both the Aristotelian intellectual virtues of 'science' and 'understanding,' and that it demonstrates just as 'science' does. But its special prerogatives concern the discussion of principles.⁽²⁹⁾

The chief goal of wisdom is the understanding of the highest cause of the particular classification under study. In philosophy, which proceeds only on the basis of evident information from the world around us, the wisdom of metaphysics, to which Thomas explicitly likens theology in *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 6, considers God, the highest cause, as he is knowable from his created effects. Sacred doctrine's consideration takes into account created effects in its consideration of God, but it also uses what Thomas calls 'effects of grace,'⁽³⁰⁾ in its attempt to know the highest cause as he knows himself.⁽³¹⁾

It is this attempt to see things as God sees himself, not unlike the way in which Thomas's understanding of Aristotelian metaphysics has the metaphysician understanding all things in virtue of their relationship to the first principle of non-contradiction, that leads to the second feature of wisdom, its concern with principles, since it through these principles, both from the orders of nature and grace, that we know God.

⁽²⁹⁾ See *Summa theologiae* I-II, q. 57, a. 2, ad 1: «Dicendum quod sapientia est quaedam scientia, in quantum habet id quod est commune omnibus scientiis, ut scilicet ex principiis conclusiones demonstrat. Sed... habet aliquid proprium supra alias scientias, in quantum scilicet de omnibus indicat, et non solum quantum ad conclusiones, sed etiam ad prima principia.»

⁽³⁰⁾ *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 7, ad 1.

⁽³¹⁾ *Ibid.*, a. 6, in corp.: «Sacra autem doctrina propriissime determinat de Deo secundum quod est altissima causa; quia non solum quantum ad illud quod est per creaturas cognoscibile, quod philosophi cognoverunt, ut dicitur Rom. 1:(19): 'Quod notum est Dei manifestum est illis'; sed etiam quantum ad id quod notum est sibi soli de seipso, et aliis per revelationem communicatum.» Note that the phrasing 'non solum... sed etiam' indicates the theologian's continued interest, and use of, principles taken from the natural order. See also *In I Sent.*, prolog., a. 4, qua. 3, ad 1: «Et ex istis principiis [of faith], non respiciens communia principia, procedit ista scientia [theology].»

Because the total power, or *virtus*, of a science is to be found in its first principles, the highest of all sciences, wisdom, must provide an account of the absolutely first principles. The account of these principles, which in theology are the articles of faith, in turn yields a necessity for two functions on the part of the wise person: 1) an explanation of the content of the principles, and; 2) the ordering of the particular discipline's principles relative to one another. In the wisdom of metaphysics, for instance, the metaphysician must explain how the first principle of non-contradiction functions, which might necessitate that he or she explicate the meaning of the terms that compose the principle: 'being,' 'non-being,' 'whole,' 'part,' and the like.⁽³²⁾ Taken to the realm of theology, this element of wisdom requires the theologian to explain what are the articles of faith, and how they function. It would also require him or her to explain the terminology and notions used in theological discussion, not only as they derive from the context of faith, but also as they derive from the order of nature. Hence a good part of what Thomas does in his theological teaching is bringing the student of sacred doctrine to an understanding of something that might actually pertain to one of the human sciences, but which is presupposed to the study of sacred doctrine.⁽³³⁾

⁽³²⁾ See *Summa theologiae* I-II, q. 66, a. 5, ad 4: «Dicendum quod veritas et cognitio principiorum indemonstrabilium dependet ex ratione terminorum; cognitio enim quid est totum et quid est pars, statim cognoscitur quod omne totum est maius sua parte. Cognoscere autem rationem entis et non entis, et totius et partis, et aliorum quae consequuntur ad ens, ex quibus sicut ex terminis constituuntur principia indemonstrabilia, pertinet ad sapientiam; quia ens commune est proprius effectus causae altissimae, scilicet Dei. Et ideo sapientia non solum utitur principiis indemonstrabilibus, quorum est intellectus, concludendo ex eis, sicut etiam aliae scientiae; sed etiam iudicando de eis, et disputando contra negantes.» This task is often referred to as the task of 'explication.' See WALLACE, *The Role of Demonstration*, pp. 58-65.

⁽³³⁾ This is the doctrine of the preambles of faith. See *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 2, a. 2, ad 1; II-II, q. 1, a. 5, ad 2. Thomas's comments just before treating the powers of the soul in general are very instructive here. See *ibid.*, I, q. 78, *in capite*: «Deinde considerandum est de potentiis animae in speciali. Ad considerationem autem Theologi pertinet inquirere specialiter solum de potentiis intellectivis et appetitivis, in quibus virtu-

The ordering of the first principles in wisdom, which, again, are the articles of faith in theology, results from the wise person's interest in understanding the first principles, since a principle could not fully be understood unless its relationship to other principles is known. In the wisdom of metaphysics, for instance, the principle 'the whole is always larger than any part,' is related to the first principle of non-contradiction, 'one cannot simultaneously affirm and deny the same thing,' because its intelligibility depends upon that first principle. In sacred doctrine the many, disparate articles of faith are interrelated, with some of them resulting from others, though they are not phrased to indicate that relationship. Elsewhere I have argued that what Thomas is doing in the very first article of the *Summa theologiae* is precisely providing the rationale for the existence of theology because of the revealed truth that the human person is ordered to the vision of God as to his or her final end. Hence two disparate 'facts' of Christian teaching, the fact of revelation itself and the fact of our special ordination to God, are linked together, with our ordination to God's being the reason for, the final cause of, revelation.⁽³⁴⁾ In fact, Thomas says that all of the articles of faith can be ordered in such a way that their collective intelligibility is reducible to two things: God's existence,

tes inveniuntur. Sed quia cognitio huiusmodi potentiarum quodammodo dependet ex aliis, ideo nostra consideratio de potentiis animae in speciali erit tripartita: primo namque considerandum est de his quae sunt praeambula ad intellectum; secundo de potentiis intellectivis; tertio de potentiis appetitivis » (my emphasis). The subsequent discussion concerns the kinds of powers of the soul, the species of the vegetative part, and the exterior and interior senses.

⁽³⁴⁾ See my «The Sapiential Character of the First Article of the *Summa theologiae*,» pp. 93-96. Interestingly, in *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 8, *in corp.*, where Thomas discusses whether theology uses argument, he notes that St Paul himself argues from the resurrection of Christ to our own, which shows that theology does not argue to prove its principles, but rather starts from its principles to show something else. Yet what we arrive at is not something we did not previously know — Christ's resurrection and our own are two different articles in the Creed — but rather the *causal* connection between Christ's resurrection and our own. The Apostle is, in fact, ordering two revealed principles so that the one is seen to be the intelligible source of the other — an ordering that is the task of wisdom.

and his having providence. ⁽³⁵⁾ And in another startling passage he claims that the entirety of Christian teaching has its source in one enunciation: « God is » (*deum esse*). ⁽³⁶⁾ Thus the wise person who traces through the various intelligible links to be found among the various principles of his or her discipline, be it metaphysics or theology, develops a knowledge of the subject that enjoys an ever-increasing simplicity, because he or she can know one or many principles in another principle that is prior to them in intelligibility. The one who knows what the redemption of humanity fully means, knows the Incarnation and the Passion. The one who knows the elevation of the human person to the vision of God in heaven, knows the existence of faith and theology.

The wise person, finally, must tend to the defense of the principles of the study he or she is involved in, be it metaphysics or sacred theology. It is the wise person who fields objections, and, in virtue of his or her knowledge of the links to be found among the claims of his or her discipline, locates the source of the objector's error and corrects it. For the theologian this can

⁽³⁵⁾ See *Summa theologiae*, II-II, q. 1, a. 7, *in corp.*: « Dicendum quod ita se habent in doctrina fidei articuli fidei sicut principia per se nota in doctrina quae per rationem naturalem habetur. In quibusdam principiis ordo quidam invenitur, ut quaedam in aliis implicite contineatur, sicut omnia principia reducuntur ad hoc sicut ad primum: 'Impossibile est simul affirmare et negare', ut patet per Philosophum in *IV Metaphysicorum*. Et similiter omnes articuli implicite continentur in aliquibus primis credibilibus, scilicet ut credatur Deus esse et providentiam habere circa hominum salutem, secundum illud *Ad Hebr.* 11:(6): 'Accedentem ad Deum oportet credere quia est, et quod inquirentibus se renumerator sit.' In esse enim divino includuntur omnia quae credimus in Deo aeternaliter existere, in quibus nostra beatitudo consistit; in fide autem providentiae includuntur omnia quae temporaliter a Deo dispensantur ad hominum salutem, quae sunt via ad beatitudinem. Et per hunc etiam modum aliorum subsequentium articulorum quidam in aliis continentur, sicut fide redemptionis humanae implicite continentur et incarnatio Christi et eius passio et omnia huiusmodi. »

⁽³⁶⁾ *Ibid.*, q. 16, a. 1, *in corp.*: « ...in fide multa continentur ordinata ad fidem qua credimus deum esse, quo est primum et principale inter omnia credibilia, ut dictum est. » Note that the term 'principale' has the notion of 'source' or 'principle' here. The reference Thomas makes is to the text found in the previous note.

mean, given his or her concern with both philosophical and theological truth, dealing with philosophical or theological error. Thus Thomas disputed as regards theological truths, say, over whether charity really exists in the Christian's soul or is a way simply of referring to the presence of the Holy Spirit, as Lombard claimed. But he also argued with those whose philosophical account of the human soul entailed the denial of personal immortality and responsibility, as happened in the Averroist crisis concerning the unity of the intellect. ⁽³⁷⁾

This sketch of what the theologian as 'wise' must do should indicate that Thomas's model for theology has the theologian doing much more than drawing conclusions from the articles of faith, as one might infer from a reading of Chenu's account. As Thomas sees it, the theologian's tasks have more to do with a penetration into the intelligibility of the revealed truths, their order, and defense. ⁽³⁸⁾ And this means that the theologian's concern with the truths of faith will require him or her to gain a certain mastery in other disciplines, particularly the philosophical disciplines. He or she must learn logic, in order to detect fallacious theological argumentation, on the one hand, and to ensure rigor in his or her own thinking, on the other. Ethics is also a necessity, since the theologian will have to identify precisely which acts pertain strictly to divine law, and which to natural law. How will the theologian be able to defend, say, the immutability of God without using notions of 'cause' or 'change' mastered in the discipline of metaphysics? Moreover, how will he or she be able fully to understand theology's principal source, the sacred scriptures, without an understanding of language, signification, analogy and metaphor, treated in works like Aristotle's *On Interpretation*? It is easy to see that the wisdom of theology, as Thomas sees it, commits the theologian to grueling preparation for its many tasks. Yet the reward for

⁽³⁷⁾ See WEISHEIPL, *Friar Thomas*, pp. 272-279.

⁽³⁸⁾ For a schematized account of the many tasks of theology, see the table provided by Muñiz, in his « De diversis muneribus S. Theologiae, » between pp. 120-121.

this hard work is a God-like understanding of things, for Thomas's sapiential notion of theology results, I believe, in the astounding doctrine that theology can best be modeled as 'God's knowledge in our frail mind.'

GOD'S KNOWLEDGE IN OUR FRAIL MIND

The quotations in the epigraph to this article show that Thomas thought that the teaching of faith gives the believer a special perspective when he or she thinks about things, for the point of view is not just what we can come to understand about the world, and God, on our own powers, but what we can know about the world and God on our own *and* with him as our guide. What the Christian knows is the very same thing God and the blessed know, because God communicates to the Christian not only truth that the Christian could gather alone, but also truth that he or she could never gather alone: the very secrets of God. And with the help of Aristotle's intellectual virtue of wisdom as a model, the theologian not only can know the individual items God knows, but can also work at approximating the simplicity of God's knowledge, since the careful ordering of principles in wisdom results in the theologian's seeing many revealed truths in one revealed truth, as St Paul sees our resurrection of Christ in 1 Corinthians (15:12-19).

Yet this knowledge puts immense stain on our minds, since human beings are on the lowest level of the intellectual order. And all of our intellection has its origin in sense knowledge, to which we must always return.⁽³⁹⁾ So, even though through God's bounteous self-giving we have knowledge we would never otherwise have, we still know through sensible things, in our stepwise fashion.⁽⁴⁰⁾ It is God's knowledge, but it is in our weak minds.

⁽³⁹⁾ See *Summa theologiae*, I, qq. 84-89.

⁽⁴⁰⁾ See *In Boethii de trin.*, q. 6, a. 3, *in corp.*: « Unde quamvis per revelationem elevemur ad aliquid cognoscendum, quod alias esset nobis ignotum, non tamen ad hoc quod alio modo cognoscamus nisi per sensi-

Yet Thomas's final view of theology does not border on agnosticism. His embracing of the model of wisdom when he presents theology as a discipline simply means that, despite the difficulty of understanding God, the theologian can make slow, steady progress towards a more unified understanding of faith as he or she properly identifies the principles of faith, comes to understand their content, and their order relative to one another. The theological profession, the fruit of much study,⁽⁴¹⁾ will not result in this life in the perfect simplicity of the knowledge that God and the blessed enjoy — the simple apprehension of God. But it will be a fuller 'foretaste of future beatitude,'⁽⁴²⁾ a beatitude that will make us like God, for we shall see him as he is (*1 John* 3:2).

MARK F. JOHNSON

ABSTRACTUM

Norunt omnes sacram doctrinam vel theologiam ut scientiam aristotelicam accipisse commentatores Thomistici tum antiqui tum moderni. Sed constans de theologia atque integra sententia Angelici in plus viget, cum aliquantulum ipsae scientiae Dei nostra cognitio theologica ab ipso Thoma frequenter assimilaretur, quod quidem 'sapientiae' magis convenit, quam mere 'scientiae.'

bilia.» This is also why Thomas says that sacred scripture must use visual images and metaphors. See *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 9, *in corp.*

⁽⁴¹⁾ See *Summa theologiae*, I, q. 1, a. 6, ad 3.

⁽⁴²⁾ This is Thomas's 'formal' definition of faith. See *ibid.*, II-II, q. 2, a. 3; q. 4, a. 1, *in corp.*: « Si quis ergo in formam definitionis huiusmodi verba reducere velit, potest dicere quod fides est habitus mentis, *qua inchoatur vita aeterna in nobis*, faciens intellectum assentire non apparentibus » (my emphasis).